

IMPROVEMENT OF LIBRARY AND READING CULTURE AMONG YOUTH AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

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Annotation: Spirituality plays an important role in shaping the reading culture among young people. Reading books fosters spiritual and intellectual growth, ultimately contributing to the development of a well-rounded, mature, and perfect individual. In particular, the ideas, teachings, and works of Eastern thinkers offer valuable insights into key concepts such as personal development, spiritual enrichment, patriotism, and education.

Keywords: Spirituality, youth, culture, reading, perfection, ideas.

In the views of Abu Rayhan Beruni, it is emphasized that "...a great honor has been bestowed upon man - he has been endowed with intelligence and strength. For this reason, in order for a person's spiritual image to correspond to the tasks set before him, he must be highly moral, knowledgeable, and enlightened...". Enlightenment, enlightenment, and perfection are achieved primarily through reading and through thorough mastery of the secrets of science. The closest helper in this regard is the book. The book is a unique miracle created by mankind.

Also, urgent tasks are envisaged, such as publishing high-quality books that meet the spiritual, educational, artistic and aesthetic needs of the population, primarily young people, assisting the activities of publishing houses and creators, supporting the publication of literature for children, translating the best examples of national and world literature, improving the culture of reading, developing a reading culture in remote regions of the republic and among young people, systematically studying the level of reading and interest in books among the population, organizing projects and competitions aimed at developing a reading culture.

The development of a system for assessing the effectiveness of measures taken to develop reading, the introduction of ratings such as "The best reading area", "The best reading neighborhood", "The best reading educational institution", and other important tasks have been set.

When it comes to reading culture, it is first necessary to provide young people with information and understanding about the rules and types of reading. Reading is a complex type of speech activity, which has two aspects:

namely, the technical aspect - mastering reading and speed reading skills, and the creative aspect - selecting the necessary information from the text.

The following types of reading are distinguished according to the level of mastering the content of the source being read: review reading - to get a general impression; introductory reading - to understand the general content; detailed reading - to understand the meaning in depth. The types and types of reading are indicated. Review reading is usually carried out before introductory and study reading. It is used when it is necessary to get acquainted with the content of the book, its chapters and paragraphs, and the author of the work. In the process of review reading, the title page, table of contents, some headings and sentences are usually read. This information itself helps to decide how much this source is needed.

Introductory (selective) reading is used to extract specific questions from several sources, as well as compare and contrast the information received, to develop your own view on this issue.

Exploratory reading is an active type of reading. It is used when you read attentively, dwell on the information, and think. It is designed to understand the main idea of the text, its purpose, the logic of the arguments, and search for answers to the questions posed to you. This type of reading requires a sequence in studying the material (by paragraphs, chapters, parts), leads to the formation of a personal opinion about the text, and forms the skill of critical perception of information.

A modern legal framework for publishing has been created in our country. Over the past period, more than 10 laws and more than 30 by-laws have been adopted. 1,677 printing enterprises and 118 publishing houses have been registered. The National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, equipped with advanced technologies, 14 regional information and library centers, about 200 information and resource centers in educational institutions in districts and cities provide information and library services to the population, and the book trade services are provided by the complexes "Kitob Olami", "Sharq Ziyokori" and "Uzdavkitobsavdota'minoti". The "Ijod" public fund, established under the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, publishes the first books of writers and poets, especially young creators, in many thousands of copies.

Today, there are 9,576 information and library institutions in the public education system, of which 12 are regional, 199 are district (city) and 928 are school information and resource centers, and 8,648 are school libraries. A total of 4,047,738 students are members of them. Information and resource centers

and libraries currently have a total of more than 23 million books. In order to enrich their book fund, fiction is purchased for students for extracurricular reading every year .

In order to promote reading among students, various cultural, educational, and intellectual events are being held. In order to promote and encourage reading among students and their parents, educational events such as "Book Presentation", "Literature Days", "My Book-My Sun", a charity event "School-Library-Family-Public Organizations" and "Three Books for One Child" campaigns with the participation of parents, as well as the "Best Bookworm" and "Bookworm School" competitions have been organized in educational institutions.

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